

Optimisation of preheating and interpass temperature in WADED magnesium alloy AZ61: A comparative study on microstructure, residual stresses, and internal defects

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Abstract: This study examines the effect of base material preheating on Wire Arc Direct Energy Deposition (WA-DED) of AZ61 magnesium alloy. The influence of preheating on the geometry and penetration behaviour of a single deposit was first evaluated and used to define suitable conditions for stabilising layer width in thin-walled structures. Two preheating strategies were examined, demonstrating that preheating the base material to 200 °C combined with the same interpass temperature provides the highest layer width stability and improved layer uniformity. The effect of preheating on residual stress was subsequently assessed through the analysis of base material deformation, revealing a reduction in residual stress of up to 50 % compared with fabrication without preheating. Furthermore, microstructural characterisation and μ CT analysis were performed to investigate porosity formation mechanisms in the deposited material. Preheating was found to have a positive effect on wall thickness stabilisation, residual stress reduction, and porosity mitigation. Based on the combined evaluation of geometric stability, residual stress, and internal defects, a temperature of 250 °C was identified as the most suitable preheating and interpass temperature for WA-DED of AZ61 magnesium alloy.

Keywords: Magnesium alloy, preheating, interpass temperature, WADED, WAAM, AZ61

Magnesium alloys, which exhibit low density and a high strength-to-weight ratio, are increasingly used in industries where the product's final weight is crucial. For example, reducing weight while replacing aluminium and steel automotive parts with magnesium can reach up to 50%¹. The use of such parts in the automotive and aerospace industries allows for a reduction in fuel consumption, resulting in more economical and environmentally friendly vehicle operation¹⁻⁴. Furthermore, the excellent heat dissipation performance and electromagnetic and radio frequency shielding properties of Mg alloys make them good candidates for commercial portable 3C products and military electronic devices^{1,5}. Together with its high recyclability, magnesium alloys, as stated in recent review articles^{2,3}, are considered the most promising green engineering materials in the 21st century. However, the production of magnesium parts is limited due to the hexagonal crystal structure and the limited number of easily activated slip modes. Therefore, magnesium alloys exhibit plastic deformation anisotropy, limiting the use of traditional manufacturing processes based on plastic deformation. Thus, 90% of magnesium-based parts are produced by casting^{6,7}. This represents the most economical manufacturing route for transforming magnesium alloys into shaped components. Still, it is also connected with numerous casting defects and the production of scrap metal^{6,8,9}.

The above-mentioned limitations of magnesium are the driving force behind the improvement of conventional techniques and the development of new manufacturing methods. One of the primary research directions suggested in the literature¹⁰ is the further improvement of advanced processing technologies for Mg alloys. Various Additive manufacturing (AM) techniques have been the subject of magnesium research in recent years due to their many advantages over conventional technologies, such as free-forming and complex shape manufacturing with excellent dimensional stability and high material efficiency^{4,10}.

One of the most explored AM techniques for metals is Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF). Although research on magnesium alloys shows promising results^{6,8,11,12}, LPBF is associated with high machine costs, size limitations, complicated process optimisation, and concerns regarding powder handling and storage, as well as safety issues. Moreover, magnesium alloys with low melting point temperatures are highly susceptible to evaporation due to localised heat and process complications resulting from melt pool instability^{13,14}.

Another AM technique highly preferable for the deposition of Mg alloys is Wire Arc Direct Energy Deposition (WADED), also known as Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM). This process utilises a wire feeder system, an electronic arc heating source and an industrial robot. During the process, filler metal wire, shielded by inert gas, is heated through an electric arc and deposited as a bead on the base material. A controlled atmosphere chamber is not required, leading to more efficient use of shielding gas. WADED is widely used in the rapid prototyping of large parts due to its high deposition rate, high material utilisation rate, and low cost^{2,6,15,16}. Unlike the LPBF technique, WADED is not constrained by platform or build chamber size. However, arc-based additive manufacturing presents challenges, as several process parameters must be monitored, and optimisation is necessary¹⁵. That is crucial to addressing common WADED challenges, including insufficient or excessive penetration, residual stress, deformation caused by high heat input, reduced dimensional accuracy, formation of cracks and porosity^{16,17}.

Regions with increased porosity in the welds are formed mainly due to hydrogen, either as an impurity in the weld material and/or base metal or from the air humidity. The magnesium surface is covered by magnesium oxide when exposed to the atmosphere. If moisture is present, the oxide is converted to magnesium hydroxide¹⁸, which can be easily introduced to the melt pool during welding. The hydrogen solubility in molten magnesium is relatively high and decreases substantially during cooling, resulting in the formation of pores¹⁹. Such inhomogeneity can act as a stress concentrator, reducing the mechanical performance of the final product. Also, when internal stresses, caused by the high coefficient of thermal expansion of magnesium, are generated during the welding process, cold cracks can initiate from the pores in solidified weldments.

The formation of cold and hot cracks when welding magnesium alloys is a topic that has been widely discussed in connection with WADED technology. Various studies^{9,10,20,21} have shown that crack size and susceptibility to crack formation during welding increase with the magnitude of electric current and heat input. Additionally, a higher aluminium content in magnesium alloys can increase their susceptibility to cracking.

Various mechanisms can form hot welding cracks in magnesium alloys. During solidification, when part of the weld metal is already solidified, but regions with higher concentrations of alloying elements remain in the liquid state, internal stresses can result in cracking at the interface. Similarly, cracks are formed in the heat-affected zone at the interface between the solid solution and the liquified low-melting-point phases. Furthermore, Huang et al.²⁰ experimentally demonstrated that multiple thermal cycles, simulating multiple welding passes, increase internal stress and hot cracking susceptibility in AZ magnesium alloys. Such facts are important for the optimisation of the WADED process, because previously deposited layers are affected in the same manner as the heat-affected zone during the building process. The quality of interfaces between layers not only affects the final quality of multilayer components but also indicates issues in the building process.

Although the principles of welding crack formation can be applied, as they primarily depend on microstructure and the presence of internal stress, differences in residual stress distribution between WADED components and multi-pass welds have been experimentally demonstrated through numerical modelling and experimental verification²². Besides crack formation, internal stress also results in deformation of the final WADED parts^{17,23,24}, especially in thin walls. The magnitude of residual stress varies with the progress of the deposition^{17,22-24}, depending on the number of layers, dimensions of the base material, and welding parameters^{17,23,25}. For multilayer components, deposition pattern is also significant influential factor and mitigation of residual stress can be achieved by use of deposition patterns with short track length^{22,24}. Thermomechanical model tested for thin walls of Inconel, Incoloy and stainless steel

showed, that preheat temperature, more specifically difference between solidus and preheat temperature, is far more influential for residual stress magnitude than base material thickness or welding parameters²³. On the contrary, experimental work on an aluminium alloy²⁵ showed the predominant effect of substrate thickness on residual stress distribution over interlayer temperature and the number of layers.

In addition to overall defects, thin walls produced by WADED are prone to non-stability in layer width, also known as necking. Such a defect appears in the first few layers before the balance between heat input and heat dissipation of the molten pool is established²⁶. Different layer widths have been observed in aluminium²⁷ and magnesium²⁶ alloy thin walls. Necking in AZ80 magnesium alloy was related to the temperature change of the base material, which heated up rapidly up to 150 °C during the fabrication of the first five layers. After that, the width of the layers remains stable²⁶. A similar phenomenon was observed for the temperature fields in a titanium alloy multilayer component²⁴. A steady state of temperature fields was achieved at the third layer, resulting in a stable stress distribution, but an increasing magnitude.

In theory, to maintain the welding parameters for optimum penetration in the WADED process, we can prevent necking, component deformation and cracking due to residual stress by minimising the temperature gradient, either by lowering the heat input or by preheating the substrate. It has been experimentally proven that increasing the interpass temperature from 50 to 100°C can reduce internal stresses by ~20% in aluminium alloy²⁵. Preheating to 350°C reduces residual stress in mild steel by 39% and 54%, depending on the direction relative to the deposition direction²⁸. Another approach to mitigating the thermal gradient is to minimise heat input during deposition by using progressive techniques or process modifications. In contrast to using a conventional power source, the Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) process, in which the wire is retracted after the short circuit, effectively mitigates the defects mentioned above due to its controlled heat input¹². This method reduces heat input by approximately 33% compared to conventional welding power sources and minimises spatter²⁹. Experimental work on aluminium alloy³⁰ also showed that the use of the CMT process leads to a smaller, colder, and faster cooling melt pool, which results in lower pore content.

Despite extensive research on WADED of aluminium and steel alloys, and isolated studies on magnesium alloys, the combined influence of substrate preheating and interpass temperature on microstructure evolution, residual stress development, and internal defect formation in AZ61 magnesium alloy processed by CMT-WADED has not yet been systematically investigated. In this study, the influence of preheating and interpass temperature on the microstructure, porosity, and residual stress of an AZ61 multilayer sample prepared by CMT-WADED was evaluated. As the first step of the deposition optimisation process, the influence of parameters and preheating on single-deposit samples with various preheating temperatures was tested. As the next step, width changes in thin walls were analysed, and the use of two preheating strategies as compensation was tested. Based on the obtained results, a process for multilayer thin-walled samples was designed, and a series of samples was fabricated with various preheating temperatures and analysed.

Materials and methods

Experimental setup

All welding experiments were conducted using a Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) power source, Fronius TPS 3200 CMT, paired with a KUKA KR 60 HA 6-axis robotic arm, controlled by Rhinoceros 6 software. During the tests, a constant speed of the welding torch (WS) of $10 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and a distance of 13 mm from the manufactured part were maintained. Pure argon (99.5%) was used as the shielding gas with a flow rate of $18 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The AZ61 wire, with a diameter of 1.6 mm and the chemical composition given in Table 1. was used as the filler material. In the previous work³¹, the filler wire was manually cleaned with SiC paper. In the present study, a custom-built automatic rotary device was used to remove surface impurities. After mechanical cleaning, the wire was annealed at $380 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 11 minutes to convert residual magnesium hydroxide into magnesium oxide, which has less adverse effect on the magnesium welding process¹⁹. The base material, an AZ31 alloy plate, was mounted on a custom preheating table with overall dimensions of $450 \times 550 \text{ mm}$, an output of 3.2 kW, and a maximum preheating temperature of $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a precision of $\pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AZ61 magnesium alloy wire

Elements	Al	Zn	Mn	Si	Fe	Cu	Ni
Max (%)	6.50	1.50	0.40	0.10	0.005	0.05	0.005

Two sets of process parameters, listed in Table 2, were used: reference parameters (REF), established in previous work³¹ for AZ91 base material, and a second parameter set designed to achieve a deeper weld penetration (DWP) on the AZ31 base material used in this study. Welding parameters, such as I_{boost} , $t_{I_{\text{boost}}}$, and $I_{\text{sc_wait}}$, directly influence the geometry of the interface between the deposited material and the base material or a previously deposited layer. This relationship has been systematically investigated in previous study³¹. For adequate interlayer bonding, the underlying layer must be sufficiently remelted along the entire interlayer interface to avoid lack-of-fusion defects³². At the same time, excessive penetration and remelting should also be avoided, as excessive remelting increases local heat input, leading to higher thermal gradients and potentially promoting distortion and the accumulation of residual stress. Accordingly, welding parameters must be optimised in conjunction with the preheating temperature, which also influences the interlayer interface geometry and remelting behaviour.

Table 2. CMT parameters used for WADED

Parameters description	Abbreviation	I_{boost} (A)	$t_{I_{\text{boost}}}$ (ms)	$I_{\text{sc_wait}}$ (A)	$vd_{\text{sc_wait}}$ ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$)	I_{sc2} (A)
Reference parameters (developed in prev. study)	REF	430 A	2,5 ms	30 A	$30 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	50 A
Deeper weld penetration parameters	DWP	400 A	3,5 ms	30 A	$30 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	50 A

Filler wire, cross-section specimens from single-deposit samples and thin walls were used for metallographic observation. Samples were prepared in the usual way, ground with SiC papers and polished with diamond pastes. Some samples were etched using an etchant based on acetic and nitric acid to reveal microstructural features. Optical microscopes, Olympus SZX7 and Zeiss Axio Observer Z1m, were used for observation and documentation. A scanning electron microscope with a field emission gun, Zeiss AG Ultra Plus, was used for more detailed observation and chemical analysis.

Experimental plan and workflow

In this work, the influence of preheating and interpass temperature on the microstructure, porosity, and residual stress of multilayer samples was investigated. Preheating temperatures in the range of 50 to 350 °C were selected based on values commonly applied during welding of AZ-type magnesium alloys¹⁸.

At first, the penetration depth and geometry of single-bead deposits produced at various preheating temperatures were investigated to establish suitable limits for subsequent multilayer fabrication. In the next step, changes in wall width with an increasing number of deposited layers were analysed in order to prevent necking in the lower part of the samples, and two preheating strategies were proposed and experimentally tested. Based on these results, a deposition process for thin-walled multilayer samples was designed, and a series of samples was fabricated under different preheating conditions and subsequently analysed.

Figure 1 illustrates the overall methodology of the present work in the form of a flowchart. Each experimental step is described in greater detail in the following sections.

Fig. 1. Experimental methodology of the present work

Single-deposit samples

Two sets of eight single-deposit samples were fabricated with different preheating temperatures, namely 50°C, 100°C, 150°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C and 350°C, including a reference sample fabricated without preheating. Each single-deposit weld bead was 50 mm long. The first set was produced using the REF parameters; for the second set, DWP parameters were used.

After production, an optical 3D scanner (ATOS Triple Scan III) was used to measure all samples. Based on the scanned data, the height and width of the weld bead were evaluated using GOM Inspect 2018 software. Values were measured in six sections through the central part of the sample. For further examination of weld penetration depth, three cross-section samples from the central part of each single-deposit weld bead were cut and prepared for metallographic observation.

Layer width stabilization samples

Thin-walled samples consisting of 15 layers with a length of 50 mm and a layer height of 2.6 mm were fabricated without preheating in order to determine the width change with increasing number of layers. The width of the individual layers was measured using an optical 3D scanner (ATOS Triple Scan III) and evaluated at 15 levels with an offset of 2.6 mm.

Two strategies were proposed for preheating optimisation and tested at a preheating temperature of 200 °C. For the first strategy, the base material was preheated to 200 °C and the thin wall was fabricated with an interpass temperature of 200 °C (Strategy_200°C). For the second strategy, the base material was preheated to 200 °C, and three layers were fabricated with an interpass temperature of 200 °C. The rest of the sample was manufactured with an interpass temperature of 50 °C without preheating (Strategy_200/50°C). The number of layers fabricated with a higher interpass temperature was chosen based on the width changes observed in thin-walled parts fabricated without preheating.

Thin-walled samples

Based on the results from previous steps, six thin-walled samples consisting of 10 layers, with a length of 60 mm, and a layer height of 2.6 mm, were fabricated using REF parameters and preheating temperatures from 50 °C to 300 °C. Interpass temperatures were equal to the preheating temperature for the fabrication of the whole sample.

The thin-walled sample production configuration is inspired by general principles used in the Bridge Curvature Method, applied in LPBF, for the rapid assessment of the influence of process parameters on residual stress³³. The base material was mounted to the heated table on only one side of the sample, as depicted in Fig. 2, and scanned using a handheld optical scanner (Scantech SIMSCAN 22). After the fabrication, the thin-walled sample was allowed to cool down to room temperature and scanned again. Both scans were aligned and measured using GOM Inspect 2018 software to assess the deflection in the direction normal to the preheating table surface, which occurs due to residual stress resulting from a large temperature gradient within the material. Measured plastic deformation was then used for comparative analysis of the residual stress in the samples produced at different preheat and interpass temperatures.

Fig. 2. Thin-walled specimen used for analyzing residual stress-induced deflection

All produced samples were inspected using a μ CT system (Procon CT-Alpha) to analyse the relative material density. Specimens were scanned at a 45 μ m isometric voxel resolution using a cone-beam μ CT device. The voltage was set to 230 kV while the applied current was 200 μ A. A copper filter was used to minimise beam hardening effects. The pore distribution, shape, and size were evaluated using the VGStudioMax 2023.1, using an ISO50 threshold and a minimum of eight voxels for a segmented pore.

For further examination, cross-section samples approximately 20 mm from the end of each sample were cut and prepared for metallographic observation. Samples were used for microstructural analysis and grain size evaluation according to ASTM E112-13, utilising the line intercept method and ImageJ image analysis software.

Results and discussion

Geometry of the single-track weld bead

The measurement results regarding the influence of base material preheating temperature on the geometry of a single-track weld bead indicate that increasing the preheating temperature leads to an increase in bead width and penetration depth, while reducing the weld bead height. The results and selected cross-sections of the weld bead preheated to a temperature of 250°C are shown in Fig. 3.

The weld bead height decreased from 4.08 mm to 2.75 mm (32.6%) for REF parameters and from 4.25 mm to 4.16 mm (2.1%) for the DWP parameters as can be seen in Fig. 3a. The results show that the DWP parameters with lower I_{boost} current and its longer duration result in a slower downward trend and significantly reduce the influence of preheating on decreasing weld bead height.

The effect of preheating on the weld width is very significant for both welding parameter sets. The weld width of the REF samples increased from 7.23 mm to 11.3 mm (56.4%) and from 9.18 mm to 12.19 mm (32.8%) for DWP samples. Both lines in Fig. 3b. show a similar growth trend and similar standard deviations, indicating comparable weld width stability.

The samples produced with the REF parameter settings did not achieve a sufficient penetration depth until they were preheated to temperatures over 100°C (Fig. 3c). Up to this temperature, weld penetration occurred only locally along the length of the weld bead, and cohesion with the base material was minimal. Stable penetration depth was observed from a preheating temperature of 150°C to 350°C, where the penetration depth increased from 0.3 mm to 1.15 mm. Additionally, samples preheated to a temperature below 200 °C exhibited a higher porosity concentration at the interface between the weld bead and the base material, which was likely caused by surface contaminants or corrosion residues⁷.

Fig. 3. (a) High (b) width (c) penetration depth of single-track weld bead (d) cross-section of selected samples

For the DWP samples, the parameter change resulted in a significant shift in the penetration depth. In the sample without preheating (20°C), the penetration depth was 0.37 mm, and gradually increased to 2.26 mm for a preheat of 350°C. The weld penetration depth growth trends in Fig. 3c are similar for REF and DWP parameter sets. However, a noticeably higher standard deviation of penetration depth is observed for the DWP parameters, indicating reduced penetration stability along the weld length. At a preheating temperature of 250 °C, both REF and DWP parameter sets result in continuous penetration along the entire interface between the deposited material and the base material, as shown in Fig. 3d.

Layer width stabilisation

This part of the optimisation aimed to eliminate wall necking in the first layers of thin wall caused by enhanced heat sinking through the base plate within the first few layers²⁷. Such a phenomenon can be significant because magnesium alloys have good thermal conductivity; therefore, a longer period is required to establish a balance between heat input and heat dissipation of the molten pool²⁶. However, as the necking is caused by a temperature gradient between the substrate and the molten pool, it can be compensated or even eliminated by preheating the substrate. In the first phase, two thin-walled samples with REF and DWP parameters were produced and scanned (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Preheating of thin walls to eliminate necking, a) REF and DWP parameters without preheating, b) REF parameters with preheating at 200°C and 200/50°C

The width of the first layer of a thin wall produced with DWP parameters corresponds to 10 mm, the average wall width is 15.5 mm, so the percentage increase is 54.4%. This change in width is significant and cannot be compensated by the preheating alone. In addition, the wall produced with DWP parameters exhibits significantly unstable behaviour across the height of the sample. For this reason, the DWP parameters were assessed to be unsuitable for producing multi-layer thin walls. They were not used to produce further samples.

The width of the first layer of a thin wall produced without preheating with REF parameters corresponds to 7.9 mm. The average wall width is 8.6 mm, resulting in an 8.7% increase. The observed necking can be compensated by preheating. According to the single-deposit experiment, the first layer should reach the required width already at a preheating temperature of 150 °C. However, due to insufficient penetration during preheating at 150 °C while using REF parameters, a minimum suitable preheating temperature of 200 °C was selected for optimisation. This temperature should ensure the minimum required penetration along the entire interface between the deposited material and the base material and, at the same time, sufficient width of the first layer.

Subsequently, two samples were produced using the Strategy_200°C and Strategy_200/50 °C approaches. Stable layer width with no significant difference between the first and remaining layers was observed for the sample produced by Strategy_200°C (see Fig. 4b). The width of the first layer was 10 mm, the average layer width was 10.3 mm, and the percentage increase was only 3.2%. At the same time, a reduction in the height of the individual layers was observed, resulting in a decrease in the overall height of the sample, which was 34.6 mm. For comparison, the height of the sample produced with REF parameters without preheating was 39.5 mm. When using Strategy_200/50°C, a slight decrease in layer width was observed after the third layer, from 10.8 mm on the first layer to 8.7 mm, with an average layer width of 9.5 mm, corresponding to a 17.5% reduction in width. Overall, this strategy led to poorer layer width stability across the sample height. On the other hand, there was no significant reduction in layer height, and the final sample measured 38.3 mm in height. It was 3.6 mm higher than the sample produced by Strategy_200°C and 1.2 mm lower than the sample with REF parameters without preheating.

While a preheating and interpass temperature of 200°C stabilises the layer width and prevents necking at the bottom, it also reduces the layer height. This should be considered when planning trajectories for producing taller, thin-walled objects, mainly to maintain a constant distance between the contact tip and the fabricated thin wall.

Thin-walled samples

Residual stress was measured indirectly as the amount of plastic deformation of the base material after deposition. The base material was fixed to the preheating table at one end, and its deflection in the direction normal to the preheating table surface, was measured. Deflection profiles along the edge of individual samples caused by plastic deformation are shown in Fig. 5b.

As can be seen from the preheating temperature–deflection dependency in Fig. 5a, up to a temperature of approximately 150 °C, preheating does not affect the amount of residual stress remaining in the thin-walled sample. In this temperature range, the maximum measured deflections were approximately 1.27 mm. In the range from 150 °C to 300 °C, a significant reduction in deformation and thus in the amount of residual stress in the body was observed. At a preheating temperature of 200 °C, the deflection decreased to 1.13 mm, and at 250 °C, it further decreased to 0.77 mm. At the maximum tested preheating temperature of 300 °C, a deflection of 0.63 mm was measured, indicating a reduction in deformation of up to 49.6%. From the shape of the curve interpolated by the measured points, it can be assumed that the results asymptotically approach a value outside the investigated preheating temperature range. Higher preheating temperatures would likely not result in further significant reductions in deformation and thus residual stress.

Fig. 5. Effect of preheating on the residual stress: (a) preheating temperature-deformation dependency, (b) plastic deformation in samples produced with different preheating temperatures

The μ CT images of individual samples with different preheat temperatures are shown in Fig. 6, along with the overall porosity ratios. The highest porosity level, 2.1%, was observed in the sample preheated to 50 °C and the lowest porosity of 0.01% was measured in the sample preheated to 250 °C. In general, overall porosity decreased with increasing preheating and interpass temperature.

As can be seen from the images, all samples contain small pores, primarily in the interlayer regions, as well as rather sizeable columnar pores. A detailed pore size analysis revealed that the majority of pores exhibit very small volumes. Most detected pores have a volume of up to 0.0007 mm³, and more than 75% of all pores in all measured samples are smaller than 0.01 mm³. The pore size distribution and the total number of pores vary with the preheating temperature; however, we can clearly see that the interlayer porosity diminishes with increasing preheat temperature, showing very low porosity ratios for samples fabricated at 250°C and 300 °C.

In contrast, samples preheated to lower temperatures exhibit large columnar pores extending across multiple deposited layers, with individual pore volumes reaching up to 48 mm³. To the best of our knowledge, such internal defects have not been previously reported in the literature^{2,6,8,12,15,19,30}. Further material analysis is presented in the following sections. Interestingly, the formation of columnar pores does not occur when higher preheating and interpass temperatures are used.

Fig. 6. Porosity measurement using μ CT scanning

All fabricated samples exhibited a layered macrostructure with a distinct interface containing coarse grains (CG) followed by very fine grains (FG). The macro- and micro-morphology of samples fabricated with preheat temperatures of 250 °C and 100 °C are shown in Fig. 7. These samples were chosen specifically because the preheat temperature of 250 °C is the lowest temperature that results in the elimination of columnar pores and low interlayer porosity. On the other hand, the sample fabricated at a preheat temperature of 100 °C contained interlayer porosity, several columnar pores, and sizable globular pores. The sample fabricated with a higher preheat temperature was fairly symmetrical; therefore, only half of the image is presented. On the contrary, the sample fabricated at a lower temperature was asymmetrical; the presence of columnar and large globular pores resulted in variations in layer height and width.

Fig. 7. Thin wall samples fabricated with preheating: (a) grain size in fine grain (FG) and coarse (CG) areas in individual layers; overall macro images of samples fabricated with preheat temperature of (b) 250 °C and (c) 100 °C; microstructures on the 1-2 layer interface of sample fabricated with preheat temperature of 250 °C and (e) 5-6 layer interface of sample fabricated with preheat temperature of 100 °C

Microstructural observations of all samples fabricated with different preheat temperatures revealed similar microstructures, including solid solution, Al-Mn-based particles, and the $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ phase, with significantly higher amounts precipitated in the top part of the samples. Depending on the preheat temperature, an increase in the quantity of the $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ phase started between layers 5 and 7. Similarly, differences in grain sizes were observed in individual layers, as seen from the grain size–layer number dependence in Fig. 7a. Each layer starts with a fine grain region (FG) and ends with a coarse grain region (CG). In a sample fabricated at a preheat temperature of 100 °C, the FG size varies between 10.24 and 13.71 μm, with stable values in the middle part of the sample and slightly smaller grains in two layers in the top and two layers in

the bottom of the sample. The CG size, on the other hand, was very small in the first layer (15.01 μm) and gradually increased up to the sixth layer (33.19 μm). It should be noted that the size difference between the fifth and sixth layers was 26%, and the difference between the sixth and seventh layers was 46%. The finer grains in the first layer can be attributed to the effective cooling achieved through heat transfer to the preheated base plate, which was preheated to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. In comparison, the maximum temperature measured on the sample was ~ 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In the sample fabricated at a preheat temperature of 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the tenth layer contained the finest grains. In contrast, the first layer contained grains of the largest size, in both the CG and FG regions. The middle part of the sample was formed by grains with sizes oscillating around 20.5 μm and 27 μm for the FG and CG regions, respectively. High values in the first layer were caused by less effective heat transfer to the base plate, which was preheated to a relatively high temperature. Additionally, a relatively high interpass temperature resulted in a higher maximum temperature measured on the sample, namely ~ 470 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fine grains in the top resulted from more effective cooling, which was least affected by the rest of the sample.

Grain sizes in all fabricated samples measured on the 3–4 (bottom) and the 8–9 (top) layer interfaces are shown in temperature dependence in Fig. 8. These specific layers were chosen as the grain size should not be affected by the position on the sample, i.e. by the peak values in the first layers or 5–6–7 layer interfaces. As can be seen from the results, grain size coarsening follows the same trend in the top and bottom areas. Most results comparing both areas show similar results with differences within the standard deviation, except for the peak value in the bottom CG area of the sample fabricated at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ preheat and interpass temperature.

Fig. 8. Average grain size in the fine grain and the coarse grain regions in samples fabricated with different preheat temperatures

Grain size in the first layers and in the top and bottom areas was clearly affected by the preheat temperature. When preheat and interpass temperatures were low enough to allow sufficient cooling via heat transfer to the base plate, the overall temperature of the sample was lower. The maximum temperature measured on the sample without preheating was ~ 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and every 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ increment in preheat and interpass temperature caused an increase in maximum sample temperature by 40 – 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. As was reported by Chen et al.³⁴, AZ61 alloy exhibits an insignificant increase in grain size at annealing temperatures up to 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, even after a 25-hour dwell time. Higher annealing temperatures of 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ result in a significant increase in grain size. Therefore, we can expect that when the maximum sample temperature exceeds 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponds to preheat and interpass temperatures of 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the grain size should increase slightly throughout the whole sample, even after 30 minutes, which is the maximum fabrication time for the presented thin-walled samples. A more significant increase in grain size is expected in samples with a maximum temperature over 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, i.e., a 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ preheat and interpass temperature. In addition, with a

higher preheat temperature, cooling is slower, and the sample is held over the critical temperature for a longer period.

The appearance and number of pores corresponded to observations using μ CT. Interlayer porosity, the number of small pores on the interface between individual layers, can be clearly visible in macrographs and micrographs in Fig. 7. The interlayer porosity is most likely caused by impurities present in the filler material. Magnesium is a highly reactive metal that readily reacts with atmospheric moisture, forming hydroxides on the wire surface. These hydroxides decompose when introduced into the melt pool, releasing hydrogen gas¹⁹. Due to the rapid solidification rate of magnesium, the gas does not have sufficient time to escape the molten pool, and surface tension traps it within the material, resulting in the formation of pores. When a higher preheat and interpass temperature is used, the overall temperature of the sample increases, allowing for slower cooling and sufficient time for gas to escape before the newly deposited layer solidifies.

A similar mechanism would explain the shape of columnar pores (see Fig. 9). Firstly, a large pore is formed during the solidification of the deposited layer. During the deposition of subsequent layers, localised remelting can occur around the trapped gas, allowing it to migrate upward and result in vertical porosity channels tilted in the deposition direction in every layer. These columnar pores were not observed in samples preheated to temperatures of 250 °C and higher, most probably due to the high overall temperature of the sample and slower solidification. On the other hand, no influence of lower preheat and interpass temperature can be observed, and the presence of columnar pores in the samples seems to be very random. This fact, along with the nonuniform distribution of interlayer porosity, suggests that even though porosity can be minimised by technological means, it is not caused by process parameters or errors in deposition.

Fig. 9. Columnar porosity formation in a WADED thin-walled sample fabricated with preheat temperature of 100 °C

A similar hypothesis, called the penetration effect, was used to explain the removal of pores from the upper part of the previous layer due to remelting by Derekar et al.³⁰, who tested the influence of interpass temperatures 50 and 100°C (with the same preheat temperature for initial layers) in Al-Mg-Mn alloy thin walls fabricated by CMT in comparison with the pulsed-MIG method. Basically, the penetration effect hypothesises that the previous layer is affected only to the extent equal to the penetration depth and shape of a single deposit. In other words, a shallow shape and a small penetration depth of the CMT deposit do not influence the interface between the two previous layers and their interlayer porosity. Samples produced with a higher interpass temperature by CMT showed a slightly higher level of porosity (0.031 vs. 0.041%) but a less uniform distribution of pores, compared to the lower temperature of 50 °C. Based on our data obtained at higher preheat temperatures, we can hypothesise that the result of Derekar et al. suggests that the temperature of 100°C also affects pores in the lower part of the previous layer to some extent, but is not high enough to allow escape of gas. This is also, to a certain extent, hypothesised by the authors and

suggested as a topic for further research. Even though the parameters of their process differ from those of our experiment, comparison is possible because they used an alloy with similar solidus and liquidus temperatures¹⁸, good thermal conductivity, and based their penetration effect hypothesis primarily on the shape and depth of penetration. Derekar et al achieved penetration ~ 1.55 mm, approximately 60% of the layer height, and our welds exhibited the same shape and penetration, only ~ 10% at a preheat temperature of 100° C and yet migration of trapped gas through the layers, resulting in the formation of columnar pores, was clearly possible.

Furthermore, a decrease of over 50% in porosity was achieved compared to a preheating temperature of 50 °C. As the significant decrease in overall porosity and complete mitigation of columnar pores in our experiment were achieved at a penetration depth of 23% (preheat temperature of 250 °C), we can assume that penetration depth is not the key factor in porosity reduction by remelting of successive layers. Derekar et al.³⁰ also compared results from pulsed-MIG and CMT. They hypothesised that the relatively low heat input from CMT cannot raise the temperature high enough to allow pores to escape by hydrogen diffusion. However, as the hydrogen diffusivity in our experimental material, magnesium, is very low compared to aluminium³⁵, including also their solid solutions (Mg) and (Al), this hypothesis is also not consistent with our results.

More detailed observations and chemical analysis were performed to explain the origin of columnar pores. As can be seen from the secondary electron micrographs in Fig. 10, the surface of the columnar pore contains a high number of particles with sizes ranging from 1.3 to 3.6 µm. Chemical analysis (Fig. 10d) confirmed the presence of aluminium and manganese in particles with no traces of iron. Even though the energy of Mn Kβ and Fe Kα are very close, the absence of signal at 7.058 keV, the energy of Fe Kβ, proves that the last peak in the spectrum belongs to manganese.

Fig. 10. (a) SEM image of columnar pore in sample fabricated with preheat and interpass temperature of 100°C, (b), (c) detailed images of particles, (d) energy dispersive X-ray spectrum of particle marked in image (c)

Further surface analysis along the columnar pore was performed to explain the presence of high amounts of secondary particles on the pore surface. Besides Al-Mn particles, higher amount of oxygen and locally traces of calcium were observed, as can be seen from image of representative area in Fig. 11. Elemental maps of Mg and Zn are not presented as the signal was detected all over the mapped area on the sample with no visible deviations, except for Al-Mn particle in central part, where less signal for Mg Kα was detected.

Higher amount of Al-Mn particles could be explained by oxide layer on the pore surface. A similar phenomenon is documented in AZ alloys castings³⁶⁻³⁸, where clusters of Al-Mn-based particles are attached to entrained oxide films. Particles in molten metal are either entrapped by entrained oxide or nucleate on entrained oxide and grow during cooling. During the WADED process, when a layer is deposited and part of the previous layer with a sizeable pore is remelted, the oxide film from the pore surface can act as entrained oxide and result in entrapment and/or nucleation of Al-Mn particles in the melt pool.

Fig. 11. (a) SEM image of the side of columnar pore with (b) energy dispersive X-ray spectrum of spot marked in image and (c) elemental mapping of marked area

Traces of Ca were observed only on the surface of the columnar pores, suggesting a deposition process as its origin, with three possible sources of contamination: shielding gas, base material and filler material. Shielding gas was supplied by a verified supplier, and no columnar pores or other contaminations were observed in other experiments while using the same batch of shielding gas. Since the columnar pores start in different layers in the thin-walled samples, we can also exclude the influence of the base material.

To confirm the origin of Ca on the surface of the pore, filler wires were analysed (see Fig. 12). As the wire after pre-treatment did not show any traces of Ca, thick oxide layer or other contaminants, analysis of the wire without pre-treatment is also presented. Microstructural components in filler wire were consistent with the microstructural analysis of thin wall deposits, but analysis of wire surface revealed a higher amount of oxygen and locally traces of Calcium (see Fig. 12c). Calcium, as part of the surface oxide layer, most probably comes from lubricants used in wire drawing processes, in which calcium stearate is very widely used³⁹ and entered the deposition process as a result of an insufficiently efficient pre-treatment of filler wire.

Fig. 12. SEM images of the wire (a) after pre-treatment and (b) before pre-treatment, (c) (d) energy dispersive X-ray spectra of areas marked in the image

The high reactivity of magnesium causes an oxide layer to form on the wire surface. As expected, pre-treatment of the filler wire before deposition is mandatory. In our previous experiments, wires were prepared manually with SiC papers, which guaranteed a clean surface of the wire, and no columnar pores were observed in the produced samples. This study employed an approach that is more suitable for industrial applications. In the first step, the wire was mechanically cleaned by a custom-built automatic rotary device and then annealed to convert any remaining hydroxides into oxides. Although the analysis of the wire after pre-treatment did not reveal any oxides or contaminants, only a few randomly chosen pieces of wire were analysed. Further analysis of filler wire and optimisation of the process are necessary to ensure that no impurities, such as Ca, can enter the deposition process.

Although the automated pre-treatment process was not as effective as the manual process and resulted in severe material defects in thin-wall samples fabricated with lower preheat and interpass temperatures, the experiment demonstrated that preheating can successfully reduce interlayer porosity. Results also suggest that preheating temperatures of 250°C and above can prevent the formation of columnar pores; however, further examination is needed to prove this hypothesis.

Despite the higher production cost associated with preheating, it significantly reduces the residual stress level and has a positive impact on thin-walled geometry. A more effective automated pre-treatment process, incorporating sufficient preheating and interpass temperature, is a promising method for producing thin-walled samples from AZ magnesium alloys by WADED.

Conclusion

This study confirmed that preheating and interpass temperature control are key to improving the quality of AZ61 magnesium alloy parts produced using the WADED method. Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Preheating to 200 °C effectively stabilised layer width, eliminated necking in the initial layers, and ensured consistent part geometry throughout the build.
- Increasing the preheating temperature reduced deflection of the base material, corresponding to a residual stress decrease. The magnitude of deflection within thin-walled parts can be reduced by up to 50% using base material preheating.
- The amount and morphology of pores were strongly affected by preheating. While low preheating temperatures led to a high level of interlayer porosity and the presence of columnar pores, these defects were almost completely suppressed at a preheating temperature of 250 °C.
- The identified optimum range of 200–250 °C represents a balance between layer stability, stress reduction, and defect minimisation, making it suitable for practical application, depending on the specific requirements of the product properties.

Although this study was limited to relatively simple thin-walled specimens, the observations form a valuable basis for extending the approach to more complex shapes. The results can contribute to streamlining manufacturing workflows and supporting more sustainable production of magnesium alloys. A logical continuation of this work will be to investigate the mechanical properties and verify the identified temperature window on geometries of higher structural complexity.

Author contributions

J.S. – Proposing research topic, conceptualization, methodology, data curation, investigation, writing – original draft, review & editing; S.Z. – methodology, investigation, writing – original draft; M.H. – methodology, investigation, writing – original draft; S.S. – technical and material support, methodology, investigation; D.K. – acquiring research funding; technical and material support, supervision.

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Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

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